

Mathematics in action: an approach in civil engineering and ecology courses

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This paper presents part of the results of a doctoral research linked to the teaching and learning of mathematics in higher education. This study aims to reflect on the ways in which mathematics can be perceived in real life contexts – this conception is known as Mathematics in Action. The data were produced from activities developed based on the perspective of Problem-Based Learning, using a qualitative approach. They were developed in Civil Engineering and Ecology courses at two public higher education institutions in the state of São Paulo, Brazil. The results show evidence that learning contexts that present mathematical formulas based on reality can favor reflections on actions or decisions based on mathematics. They also contribute to the production of other studies involving the field of mathematics education in higher education.

Introduction

In recent years, concerns about the challenges and perspectives of higher education have been the subject of international level discussions. The aspects involving the teaching and learning processes, as well as the understanding and use of knowledge, in different courses, are linked to future actions of individuals in society, whether personal or professional. As a result, concerns also emerge regarding the ways in which the teaching and learning processes occur.

These concerns also extend to the field of mathematics education. After all, the notions linked to mathematical knowledge move in several directions. Reflecting on them can stimulate the development of critical perspectives. In addition, the aspects that revolve around the teaching of mathematics can be explored through an environment that encourages investigation processes.

The main objective of this paper is to propose discussions about the perceptions of mathematics being put into action in real life contexts, which is understood in the literature as the concept called mathematics in action, proposed by Skovsmose (2006, 2014a, 2014b, 2020). The inclinations of the respective work encompass perspectives based on Problem-Based Learning (PBL). The intention was to establish greater approximations between theoretical studies involving mathematical knowledge and its practical applications projected in real life contexts.

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In the academic world in general, there are already studies related to mathematics and learning based on problems and projects in the context of universities. Among them, it is possible to mention works such as: Vithal, Christiansen and Skovsmose (1995); Christensen (2008); Hernandez, Valero and Ravn (2015); Gouvêa (2016); Souza (2016); Valero and Ravn (2017). However, there are no empirical studies related to the concept of mathematics in action in Higher Education from PBL perspectives. This is a fundamental characteristic that demonstrates the originality of this research. Making investigations possible in this sense is something relevant to students, the academic community and our society. Thus, the purpose of this study is to reflect on some learning contexts that are based on reality and the use of mathematical concepts or formulas, in two bachelor degrees: Civil Engineering and Ecology.

Initially, this paper presents the methodological perspective and some procedures used in the referred research. In addition to describing the elaboration and development of the proposed activities, which were outlined based on a real situation, inspired by the PBL. Following, the theoretical assumptions related to the development of mathematics in action, which can be perceived in reality through five performance aspects are highlighted.

To conclude, are presented discussions about elements that were present in the construction of one of the three themes elaborated from the analysis and interpretation of the data, which was entitled "Learning contexts with formulas or mathematical concepts can tell us many things". In this stage, we highlighted three aspects of mathematics in action: technological imagination, hypothetical reasoning and realization, in addition to relevant considerations about the learning principles related to PBL.

The study proposes reflections on the different ways of perceiving the presence of mathematics in real life. Actions or decisions based on mathematics can be analyzed and questioned in universities through practices that lead to reflection, in addition to collaborating with the personal and professional training of students. Contributions such as these can favor studies in the field of mathematical education and concerns related to the challenges and perspectives of higher education.

The study design

The research molds were built from a qualitative approach, which seeks to interpret in a careful way the dynamics of the observed study.

The data production stage took place at two different times, in two public higher education institutions in the state of São Paulo, Brazil, during the second semester of 2018, through weekly meetings. In the first institution, named in the research as institution A, a group of first year students of Civil Engineering participated in the investigation, during extracurricular hours. In the case of the second institution, called institution B, the participants were second year students of the Ecology course and the whole process took place during some classes in the course of Differential and Integral Calculus II.

The study and analysis of a real problem mobilized the dynamics of meetings. There were four meetings at both institutions. At institution A, activities were carried out by the researcher herself. In the case of institution B, in addition to the students and the researcher,

there was the participation of the class teacher and a research assistant, who was part of the group of studies and research in mathematics education to which the author of this paper is linked. In this same institution, the students were divided into small groups and the discussions held took place through three meetings. Furthermore, the fourth meeting was destined for the final presentation. At this stage, the students could approach themes addressed throughout the process.

All data produced were recorded through audio recordings, and the researcher wrote comments in field notes, respecting the research's ethical principles.

Regarding the data presentation, there were concerns about demonstrating the potential of the work based on the discussions generated by a particular problem. The transcription of the data resulted in the first drafts, which were read and rewritten a few times. This process culminated in the final production of two texts, presented in two distinct chapters, one focused on data produced at institution A and the other, focused on institution B.

The data analysis process was inspired by the theoretical assumptions of Creswell (2007). For the author, the constitution of the analysis occurs through some steps that range from the organization and preparation of the data to the final interpretation of the results obtained.

After carrying out the analysis some categories emerged, which led, finally, to the stage of elaboration and description of the themes. According to Creswell (2007), these themes represent the main results in qualitative studies. Furthermore, they must be based on the theoretical contributions of the study and on specific evidence related to the research issue. In this thesis, three central themes emerged, which are directly or indirectly linked to the five aspects of mathematics in action. The three themes are:

1. Learning contexts with formulas or mathematical concepts can tell us many things
2. Elaborating legitimations and justifications through mathematics
3. Reflections on responsibility, ethics and valuation

In this paper, the discussions refer to the first theme, which discusses the use of certain concepts or mathematical formulas in different situations. The contexts analyzed by the participants mobilized different reflections about possible applications of a mathematical model in reality.

The problem that was used as the guiding thread of the investigation process is presented below.

From the organization to the understanding of the problem used

The material organization that led some of the face-to-face meetings as part of the master's research developed by the researcher (Souza, 2016). Its structuring followed theoretical assumptions related to the PBL's use. At that time, four problems were elaborated, which could be worked on in the exact, humanities and natural science areas, for example. These problems were structured by the researcher based on real or potentially real contexts and, among them, there was a suggestion of possibilities to assist in conducting the activities.

Soon, during the doctorate, there was a restructuring of one of the problems presented in the dissertation, based on new theoretical contributions. The intention was to use the chosen problem as a trigger for the discussions that would be held during the face-to-face meetings, seeking to ascertain whether the choice would open up possibilities to foster different reflections, in addition to the field of mathematical education.

“Environmental impacts caused by chemical pollutants” was the title of the problem. It consisted of two approaches: one involved a description of a fire that occurred in fuel tanks, in 2015, in the Alemoa neighborhood, in the city of Santos, state of São Paulo, Brazil, causing contamination of the region and several environmental impacts: social, political and economic. The other approach called “Support study” was elaborated from some adaptations of an activity found in a Calculation book. It addressed a fictitious situation, similar to the real case that occurred in Santos, and sought to contribute to discussions related to different mathematical knowledge worked in university.

The subsequent section includes theoretical references to the themes involved in the present study.

Understanding the concept called mathematics in action

The concept called mathematics in action was developed by Ole Skovsmose and is part of the concerns associated with the field of critical mathematics education. We understand that mathematics is associated with a variety of situations and practices, like social, economic and political aspects. Thus, it is possible to propose discussions about the operationalization of mathematics in different contexts.

When talking about mathematics in action we are referring to

All those practices that include mathematics as a constituting part. It could be: technological innovation; forms of production; automation; management and decision making; financial transactions; risk estimation; cost-benefit analysis, etc. (Skovsmose, 2006, p. 323).

For this author, practices like these contain actions based on mathematics and, therefore, there is a need to promote reflections around them. In this way, this concept can be understood from five aspects: *technological imagination*, *hypothetical reasoning*, *legitimation or justification*, *realization* and *dissolution of responsibility*.

The technological imagination refers to the possibilities of exploring the construction and development of hypothetical situations in the form of technological alternatives, based on imagination. Every type of enterprise can be based on imagination, that is, on an imaginary scenario. Hypothetical situations can be raised and mathematics can provide materials for the construction of such situations.

Elaborate the hypothetical reasoning it concerns the analysis and evaluation of the possible consequences of an imaginary scenario. In other words, this aspect contributes to investigations about a given situation before an undertaking is executed or a decision is made. Mathematics can help in the approaches related to hypothetical reasoning because the hypotheses and investigations about the probable results of something not yet realized can be made through the use of mathematical models.

The construction of justifications and legitimations math based can be used for certain actions or decisions be taken. The aspect of realization takes action when the mathematics becomes part of reality in everyday life, but many effects may be hidden in these models and the categories and discourses produced from them are varied and their consequences can sometimes be pleasant and beneficial, sometimes they can present risks and disadvantages.

Finally, the dissolution of responsibility occurs when actions supported in mathematics include an exemption of liability. Normally, any action refers to an agent subject, but, in mathematics in action, that subject's performance does not seem to exist and the relevance of responsibility seems to be in charge of the mathematical model used. When addressing the question of responsibility, it is necessary to analyze whether the methods and tools used are reliable; whether the calculations performed are reasonable; whether (and which) aspects were ignored in the formulation of the model; etc.

Next, we presented some analyzes regarding the understanding of three aspects of mathematics in action constructed from the constitution of scenarios that encompass concepts or mathematical formulas.

What learning contexts involving reality and mathematical formulas can tell us

This section presents some previous results of the doctoral research. In different moments of data production, the use of some concepts or mathematical formulas in different situations mobilized many reflections. These contexts contributed to some aspects of mathematics in action that emerged during the discussions.

The construction of the theme “What learning contexts with mathematical formulas based on reality can tell us” contemplates three aspects of mathematics in action: technological imagination, hypothetical reasoning and realization. Thus, to contemplate them, another perspective is presented to approach the different mathematical content in universities.

A teacher putting different mathematical relationships on the board. A textbook or handout material. Students copying examples or solving exercises. Usually, this landscape prevails in many classes that contemplate mathematics in higher education.

The contexts presented below involve a blackboard, study materials, examples or exercises. However, everything was contemplated through the students' protagonism. The perceptions that emerged during the meetings were possible through the material delivered to the students about the case of the accident in Santos-SP. To start the discussions, the following a student's speech from institution A:

Rogério: [...] we could work with some mathematical models thinking about the influence that [the fire in Alemoa] would have on the traffic of that region. They could be linked to a project that was done or that we want to do. You can see how much this will influence the fauna, you will have to move the animals that are around and you have to have all this planning part of how much this would change in the surroundings. For example, statistical data ... I think it would be interesting to include them in the analysis to quantify how much would change and to take the respective measures to mitigate the impacts, as much as possible.

According to Rogério's speech, we understand that mathematics is associated with the aspect of *technological imagination*. The examples he describes reveal the development of hypothetical situations and show that there are possibilities to think about different alternatives based on the analysis and understanding of mathematical models and the use of statistics. The notes made by the student concern the forms of organization, know-how and procedures related to the execution of projects and undertakings, as well as decision-making.

Another issue that emerged in the discussions was present in the "Support study", and that referred to the self-purification process. At institution A, the participants worked effectively with the material delivered at the beginning of the activities. When elaborating and developing it with the students, there were no specific explanations as to the meaning of the term self-purification. Interpretations related to that word were developed over the meetings and were made by the students themselves, based on the analysis of a bay's self-cleaning ability. The following dialogue was based on the following information and took place between researcher Débora and students Luara and Renata, both from institution A.

After a careful analysis of the situation, environmental scientists have guaranteed that the bay has a capacity for self-cleaning at a rate of 20% per year.

Débora: Here I would like to ask just one question: "Ability to self-purify at a rate of 20%. What is your understanding of this?"

Luara: I don't know what self-cleaning is, but it must be related to something that is over.

Renata: I think it must be the rate that contamination takes to decrease, for example, in one year, it will return to 20% of what it was before.

The situation presented contributed to the engineering students elaborated interpretations of what would be the representation of a scenario elaborated according to this information. And the raising of these hypotheses was associated with the following mathematical model covered in the support study:

Based on this hypothesis, the specialists then established a model for the concentration of Oily Agent over time:

$$f(1) = 10$$
$$f(x+1) = 0,8f(x)$$

Soon, the students stated:

Luara: So, it will always decrease by 20% and 20%; it will remove more and more oil and there will always be a little bit leftover.

Renata: It means that the next [value] will always be 80% of the previous one.

It can be seen that although they did not have specific knowledge about self-purification, this was being built from the set of data analyzed. There was an opening for the *technological imagination* emerged. The students explored hypothetical situations based on imagination. The organization of the mathematical information constructed in this imaginary scenario allowed them to analyze and evaluate the consequences of that scenario in reality. These perceptions are in line with Skovsmose (2014b, p. 96) when he says that "one can reflect on

the nature of technological imagination supported by mathematics in view of specific issues [...]. This imagination can generate new guidelines [...] It can enable actions that otherwise would not be possible". With this, if the relations given were placed to investigate the decontamination processes in that bay, it would be necessary to put into action the *hypothetical reasoning* aspect because through it the hypothesis survey would be analyzed using the models considered.

Luara and Renata stated that self-purification was associated with the rates of decrease in the concentration of pollutants. A similar placement was also made by the ecology students, Katia and Carlos, from institution B. They highlighting other important elements:

Katia: In this process, depending on the location, if it is in the sea, in the lake, it can have a difference in oxidation. As in the seas, the current is faster and larger, it occurs faster than in the river.

Carlos: And self-purification also depends both on the speed of the watercourse and on the morphology of the riverbed or the quantity of the substance that is emptied, we can associate it with the transparency of the river.

This proved to be relevant as the analysis of the participants evolved, highlighting that as proposed by Skovsmose (2008), the analysis of an imaginary scenario is not only related to mathematics, after all, it involves other fields of knowledge. Katia and Carlos pointed out to evaluate the self-purification process, it would also be necessary to understand the location's oxidation, the speed of the watercourse, among other factors related to environmental issues. This placement of students reinforces that hypothetical reasoning should not be supported by mathematics alone. It is in line with Skovsmose (2008) when stating that in situations like these, the details of the investigation are only represented within a specific mathematical construction within a given alternative and, thus, there are limitations regarding real reasoning because the reasoning itself is founded on mathematics.

When advancing in the reading and analysis of the support study, the engineering students deepened the discussions. They hypothesized about the limit formula of a function: $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = 0$. For example, Luara, in his first perception, deduced:

Luara: I think there is a limit to how much the place can get rid of the pollutant. [...] It seems that it will never reach zero. We know that this is decreasing ...

As the readings progressed, in association with the tables and graphs of the support study, Luara and Renata elaborated more interpretations about this formula:

Luara: It makes no sense! That's because, in the given expression, x tends to infinity! So, it will only return to the natural, to the infinite ... only that we will never reach the infinite because it is infinite.

Renata: It may be a very small amount, but it will still be there.

The hypotheses raised by the students demonstrate reflections on the real impacts of applying a mathematical formula in reality, which is related to the aspect of *realization*. For them, the limit formula interpretation in the given context could be somewhat wrong. For them, the bay, would not be totally decontaminated, because even over the years there would

still be some pollutant in the place, from the spill of the oily agent. The students' statements reveal that certain effects may be hidden in a situation like this. In addition, the speeches produced from such an interpretation, could present risks and disadvantages.

Subsequently, in the context of the material used, the expression of the limit of a function was used as an argument by the defense lawyer of the company responsible for the accident. According to him, the formula supported the thesis that the cleaning of the bay would occur naturally over the years, which, therefore, would influence the value of the fine for the environmental impacts caused. Even before reaching the part of the material where this conclusion would be made, student Rogério emphasized:

Rogério: As I understand it, the damage that was caused in that environment, over time, would gradually be cured. Over time, the more it would improve, until it reached the point where he would be completely cured, so the lawyer approached this for a time equal to infinite. So based on that he gave a natural response, as if not as if there was no real damage to nature because over time she can fix things herself [...]

The student imagined a scenario constituted by the understanding of several elements that emerged during the meetings: the limit formula, the tables and graphs of the support study, the deepening of research on self-purification and, such analyzes, would influence in reality, leading us to perceive the aspect of *realization* as well.

In these analyzes it was possible to verify that the knowledge used was applied in a particular situation and new possibilities of learning, of studies, emerged from the materials and the discussions provided. With that, different actions and decisions could be taken in face of the conclusions obtained. For example, the entire context involving these self-cleaning processes would contribute to the assessment of the analyzed aquatic environment and, consequently, this would allow different actions to be planned and executed, such as the release of fishing, the ways of compensating the damages caused, among other factors.

This entire process of discussion and reflection was supported by theoretical foundations by Skovsmose. The construction of a set of hypothetical situations is a powerful act. It is understood that opening possibilities for technological imagination, hypothetical reasoning and realization to appear in higher education mathematics classes is something powerful. Thus, this opening can transform learning contexts supported by the predominance of conventional classes of the explanation-exercises-correction type.

Concluding remarks

In this paper we presented some results of a PhD research in progress. In it, it is possible to contemplate ways of approaching some aspects of mathematics in action in higher education, inspired by a work perspective based on the PBL.

We tried to highlight the path of the investigative process, describing from the organization to the stages of development of the activities carried out. There was also a concern to explain the understanding of the five aspects of mathematics in action, even though only three of them were actually worked on in the presentation of the results.

Develop this theme in the thesis revealed some research potentialities. Inspired by Skovsmose it was possible to perceive, through learning around a problem, how the mathematics in action's aspects could reveal themselves, even in different university contexts.

Learning contexts that present mathematical formulas based on reality can promote different reflections. This theme emerged from moments when participants made interpretations regarding the use of formulas, equations, mathematical indexes or even concepts related to this field of knowledge. In different circumstances they sought to understand the ways in which mathematics operated in certain situations, whether implicitly or explicitly. In certain cases, the participants seemed to perceive the context described in each case addressed. They raised different hypotheses, sought to identify and assess the possible consequences of a project, undertaking or deciding, and also seemed to understand the real application of mathematical models in their fields of activity. It is understood that these reflections were mobilized by the work with the PBL. This teaching methodology contributed to the students' concerns being expressed. The problem adopted in the investigation was used to trigger the discussions. Several of them related to technological imagination, hypothetical reasoning, and achievement. However, the notes made by the participants did not only concern mathematics. They were associated with a real event and was structured to promote reflections on social, environmental and economic aspects, for example. Furthermore, the students worked in groups, discussed real issues and problems, there were perceptions about different fields of knowledge, they deepened research involving their fields of interest and presented criticisms regarding mathematics and their future area of expertise in this case, as engineers or ecologists, etc. Finally, the elaboration of this theme aimed to highlight these perceptions, in addition to proposing discussions that aim to contribute to the field of mathematics education in universities.

This was a way of presenting some reflections in this article. By linking the mathematical field to different learning situations, it is possible to perceive the ways in which mathematics can present itself in reality. Furthermore, this allows students to reflect on the knowledge learned and analyze how the presence of mathematical models in reality can actually happen. Being aware of such perceptions is something that cannot be lacking in the field of mathematical education and this can contribute to the adoption of different critical thoughts and attitudes in society.

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